

Wide Open Science

Bill Howe, Maxim Grechkin

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Open science represents a movement to bring the incentives that drive science back in line with the stated values of science: A set of practices, norms, and tools designed to reward the sharing of knowledge in addition to the creation of knowledge.

The status quo of slow and steady culture change is likely the most realistic path forward, but it's useful to consider a more transformative vision for *wide open science*.

1 Wide Open Experiments: Least Publishable Units and an Open Hypothesis Registry

Concerns have been raised about the least publishable unit: incentive structures that maximize quantity at the expense of quality by finding the smallest possible result that can be inflated into a paper. The number of papers are going up over time per author (mostly due to a growth in the number of authors per paper; c.f. Larsen and Markus), contributing to what many perceive as an information glut and a lower signal to noise ratio in the scientific literature.

But the answer is not to encourage “bigger” papers, but to change the nature of scientific publishing to separate quantitative results from the rhetorical “housing” of a scientific paper. The idea of an LPU is a good one: an individual experimental result, with only the minimal information needed to understand it and reproduce it. A visualization of an experimental result, linked explicitly with a specific hypothesis, along with enough supporting text to interpret it and understand the conclusion and the code, data, and environment needed to recreate it.

What does this have to do with open science? Each hypothesis must be registered publicly, *before* conducting the experiment, which is consistent with open science principles. This pre-registration of intent realizes a number of benefits associated with open lab notebooks: researchers can timestamp their interest in the problem, initiate discussion among peers, sponsors, and the general public, and reduce redundancy with colleagues. But more importantly, public registration of hypotheses is important to combat publication bias and avoid multiple hypothesis testing issues. We are all rolling the dice in private and then yelling “yahtzee” when something rare happens.

Figure 1: The number of curated datasets lags far behind the number of submitted datasets in the Gene Expression Omnibus, suggesting an impediment to reuse.

An open, sponsor-mandated registry of hypotheses, experiments, and results (along with code, data, etc.) would simultaneously advance open science, reduce publication bias, encourage public discourse and feedback, and combat the glut of low-impact LPU papers. Researchers could spend more time on generating results and less time on packaging the results.

Scientific writing would simultaneously play a more important role, providing synthesis, meta-analysis, interpretation, discussion, and persuasion (just like liberal arts scholars!) But a paper would no longer need to pull double duty as both a rhetorical device and a woefully inadequate delivery vehicle for quantitative results.

2 Wide Open Data: It's Not Enough to Make Data "Available"

In some fields, funding agencies and publishers have mandated that authors post data into online repositories to improve reproducibility and encourage reuse. The existence of online repositories is not enough to meet these goals.

The Gene Expression Omnibus, an online repository for gene expression data (primarily Microarray and RNA-Seq), is a relatively successful and robust

Figure 2: The number of datasets that are overdue to be made public in the Gene Expression Omnibus has been increasing overtime (though is now decreasing since we alerted the administrators to this problem).

example of an online repository: The growth in the number of datasets hosted has been striking. However, the growth in the number of curated datasets is relatively flat (Figure 1), suggesting an impediment to reuse. Datasets may or may not even be visible: Figure 2 shows the number of datasets that are still private despite a paper being published that cites it, in violation of GEO policies.

The investment in the infrastructure for open data repositories is insufficient: we need to directly measure the stated goals: reuse and reproducibility. And once we can measure our progress, we need to bring computational approaches to bear to automatically curate, integrate, clean, and standardize available data to make reuse and reproducibility the path of least resistance; this is what we mean by Wide Open Science.

3 Wide Open Publishing: Overlay Journals, Of Course

I was recently involved in a discussion with the editors of a journal, who had rejected a paper on the basis that it had already been published on arXiv, and as a result had already received attention in the popular press. They posed the question “What value can our journal provide if the world is already aware of

the work?” My coauthors and I honestly couldn’t answer. I suppose I and my students should publish in these venues to get jobs, tenure, etc., but that’s hardly an argument in favor of the fundamentals of the current publishing model.

As part of the discussion, a very smart colleague, Jevin West, wrote this to comment on the value of pre-publishing on arXiv:

(1) Posting to the arXiv allows me to receive extensive comments on my work from the people most invested in the area, prior to publication. This in turn helps me improve my papers considerably prior to, or in parallel with, peer review. On average, the value of the comments I receive from arXiv readers exceeds that of the comments I receive from peer reviewers, probably because the arXiv readers who write them are more closely involved in the specific area of research

(2) Thirty years ago, researchers circulated paper copies of working papers in order to get this type of advance feedback; twenty years ago this was done by email. In both cases, the process created huge inequities. Top researchers at top institutions had access to a large fraction of the unpublished but circulating material; early career researchers, researchers at lesser-known institutions, researchers outside of the US, etc., had far more limited access. The arXiv levels this playing field. Everyone, from a graduate student in Bangladesh to a department chair at Princeton has the same access to the working paper literature.

So the value of the pre-print servers is clear. And the value of the traditional journals is not.

Open access journals are not fighting the right battle: they are attempting to adjust the traditional journal model top down rather than create a new model bottom up.

A paper is not necessarily better having “gotten in” to a journal, as a number of experiments have shown (in one experiment,¹ acceptance and rejection to a prestigious conference in CS was shown to be largely random for most papers). So the only value a journal provides is a mechanism to organize peer review and some curation services. It is absolutely reasonable to pay for both, assuming the financials can be arranged to not induce conflicts of interests. But it does not seem reasonable to pay for any other aspect of the publishing process. It simply doesn’t cost anything to get a paper minimally typeset, published, and permanently hosted.

Curation includes standards and conventions in format, style, methods, analysis that are also associated with journals today. These standards and conventions are valuable — they help ensure consistent peer review, facilitate understanding of complex material, and make it easier to write the paper. But these

¹<http://blog.mrtz.org/2014/12/15/the-nips-experiment.html>

standards do not need to be managed and enforced top-down through traditional journals (which may also impart unwanted inertia), but can be adopted (and adapted) ad hoc with dynamic communities.

All of these goals (reduce publication friction while enabling community-driven peer review and curation) are well-represented by *overlay journals*, where a journal-like structure is super-imposed on open access materials.

One argument against this model is that without traditional journals, it becomes more difficult for the general public, the popular press, and policy makers to distinguish bad science from good science. But we claim the current model is failing in this regard already. There is plenty of evidence for the inadequacy of the current model; one example is the fact that the number of retractions has increased over time². But moreover it has been clearly demonstrated of late that the public is less influenced by any kind of published science, prestigious or not, than by manufactured but ostensibly compelling claims, even with zero supporting evidence. So lack of proper peer review is hardly the issue — we'd prefer the public read and discuss low-quality science than outright bullshit.

²<http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0068397> Why Has the Number of Scientific Retractions Increased? R. Grant Steen, Arturo Casadevall, Ferric C. Fang